

CraftPy: Background Formulary

Form for the background of the participants in the experiment with the CraftPy tool.

- What is your degree of visual impairment?
- Which technology course are you studying or have you studied?
- How old are you?
- Do you already work in the field? If yes, what is your job?

CraftPy: Tool Formulary

Form about the experiment with the CRAFTPy tool.

- Paste the code of the completed activity in this question.
- Were you already familiar with the 3 diagrams used?
- Which screen reader did you use for the experiment?
- What are the positive aspects of the tool?
- What are the aspects of the tool that could be improved?
- Do you have any additional comments?